

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES

732559

Integrated Platform Design and Development-v1

Deliverable No.	D4.2		
WP No.	4	WP title	ToyLabs Integrated Platform Design and Development
Activity No.	T4.1/4.2	Activity Title	Collaboration Platform Design and Development
Authors	SLG, NTUA, AIJU		
Status	Final Version		
Dissemination level	Public		
File Name	TOYLABS_SLG_WP4_IR_D4.2 Integrated Platform Design and Development-v1		
Delivery date	8 January 2018		

Version History Table

No.	Date	Author	Notes and Comments
-----	------	--------	--------------------

0.1	15.11.2017	SLG	Initial ToC
0.2	25.11.2017	SLG	First Draft
0.3	20.12.2017	SLG, NTUA, AIJU	Final Draft (for Review)
0.4	28.12.2017	AIJU	Reviewed Version
1.0	08.01.2018	SLG	Final Version

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	4
LIST OF TABLES	4
ABBREVIATIONS LIST	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE.....	6
1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE	6
1.3 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS	6
2 TOYLABS PLATFORM INTEGRATION PROGRESS	7
2.1 PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE	7
2.2 INTEGRATED COMPONENTS	9
2.2.1 <i>Market Trends Analysis component</i>	9
2.2.2 <i>Partner Matching and Negotiation component</i>	13
2.2.3 <i>Augmented Reality Feedback component</i>	16
3 COMPONENTS INTEGRATION PLAN UPDATE	18
3.1 RELEASES	18
3.2 INTEGRATION PLAN UPDATE	18
4 CONCLUSIONS	19
4.1 AT A GLANCE	19
4.2 NEXT STEPS.....	19

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Platform Architecture.....	7
Figure 2: Level Integration.....	8
Figure 3: Trends Analysis Component	9
Figure 4: Market Analysis Screenshot 1/5.....	10
Figure 5: Market Analysis Screenshot 2/5.....	10
Figure 6: Market Analysis Screenshot 3/5.....	11
Figure 7: Market Analysis Screenshot 4/5.....	11
Figure 8: Market Analysis Screenshot 5/5.....	12
Figure 9: high-level architecture of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component.....	13
Figure 10: Partner Matching Screenshot 1/3.....	14
Figure 11: Partner Matching Screenshot 2/3.....	15
Figure 12: Partner Matching Screenshot 1/3.....	15
Figure 13: high-level architecture of the Augmented Reality Feedback Component.....	16

LIST OF TABLES

N/A

ABBREVIATIONS LIST

ARF	Augmented Reality Feedback
ARFC	Augmented Reality Feedback Component
MTA	Market & Trends Analysis
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PMN	Partner Matching and Negotiation
TCP	ToyLabs Core Platform

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable D4.2 titled as “Integrated Platform Design and Development-v1” is used to document the 1st prototype version of the ToyLabs integrated platform.

The deliverable has the nature of a “Demonstrator”, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the developed software, the source code of which can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

D4.2 will be updated throughout the project as the new components will be further developed and integrated, leading to a new version of the integrated platform at the end of each development circle, resulting to deliverables D4.3 and D4.4 and to the release of the stable final version of the Collaboration Platform.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and scope

Deliverable D4.2 titled as “Integrated Platform Design and Development-v1” refers to the first prototype version of the integrated Toylabs Platform which has already been released and briefly presented in the interim review of the project. The present document includes the description of the platform, while it also provides updates to the integration plan presented in D4.1, defining the steps for the next versions of the platform till the final fully integrated version.

The deliverable is of “Demonstrator” type, therefore the document at hand acts as an accompanying text to the actual software platform developed and released. The source code and the relevant documentation can be found in the project’s GitHub repository, located at <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

D4.2 is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the architecture of the Collaboration Platform v1 (ToyLabs Core Platform) delivered
- Section 3 includes the plan and the process for the integration of the added-value component
- Section 4 concludes the deliverable, stating the next imminent steps to be executed

1.3 Relation to other ToyLabs WPs and Tasks

Deliverable D4.2 is based on D4.1, updating it as far it concerns the components which have been developed and integrated to the platform. As the software platform further evolves, D4.2 will serve as the starting point for D4.3 and D4.4.

Deliverables D3.3.-D3.5 referring to the design and development of the added-value components in development circles, shall take into account the plan presented in D4.2 order all development tasks to be fully aligned towards building the final integrated version of the ToyLabs platform.

2 Toylabs Platform Integration Progress

2.1 Platform Architecture

In D4.1, the architecture of the Toylabs Core Platform has been presented. The components which have been developed since the 1st release of the platform, have been integrated following the Integration Plan also presented in D4.1. From a platform architecture scope, the three added value components are integrated through three component connectors respectively, as shown in the following diagram.

Figure 1: Platform Architecture

The first version of the integrated platform (prototype), has been released according to the integration plan delivered in D4.1 (see next diagram). Based on the plan, the three components to be integrated were not supposed to present equal progress as far it concerns the level of integration achieved.

Specifically, on the basis of the 5 Eclipse Integration Conformance Levels¹: (None, Invocation, Data, API and UI), the Partner Matching & Negotiation component has been integrated in the prototype platform in User Interface Level. This means that PMN component has been integrated in all dimensions so that it could be actually considered as part of the core platform as if they were designed as a single application.

¹ <https://www.eclipse.org/articles/Article-Levels-Of-Integration/levels-of-integration.html>

Figure 2: Level Integration

In the 1st release of the Toylabs Integrated Platform, it is already possible to have the user seamlessly move from the Core Platform to the Partner Matching and Negotiation component and back, without becoming obvious whether the component is autonomous or part of a monolithic software solution.

As far as it concerns the Market and Trends Analysis (MTA) component, its integration is (both actually and according to the schedule) one step behind PMN, having achieved API level integration and working towards the UI integration which is expected to get completed before Month 15, when the second version of the Integrated Platform will be released. At the time the present deliverable is being compiled, the MTA component works seamlessly by exchanging through APIs all the information required with the core platform. As far as it concerns the User Interface of the MTA component, it has been fully aligned to the design template and to the directions provided in order at a later stage to become fully integrated in the Toylabs Collaboration Platform.

Finally, regarding the Augmented Reality Feedback (ARF) component, it has not been actually integrated although its prototype version can be launched as an external process without having (yet) capabilities and installed mechanisms for exchanging data directly with the Core Platform.

2.2 Integrated Components

2.2.1 Market Trends Analysis component

The following diagram represents the system architecture of the MTA component. The communication/ integration to the main platform is being achieved in the middle level (communication layer) while significant progress regarding the integration at User Interface level has been also performed ahead of schedule.

Figure 3: Trends Analysis Component

.In the following screenshots, the main screens of the component are being presented. Although the interface is not yet fully integrated to the core platform, browsing the component while starting from the core platform is, for the end user, a seamless process.

In brief, users initiating the component are able to:

- Initialize the process of Data Harvesting from social media and other defined web sources
- Perform Trend Analysis in the domain based on given parameters
- Collect and analyze Customers' Feedback as expressed in the web and the social networks

Figure 4: Market Analysis Screenshot 1/5

Figure 5: Market Analysis Screenshot 2/5

Figure 6: Market Analysis Screenshot 3/5

Figure 7: Market Analysis Screenshot 4/5

Figure 8: Market Analysis Screenshot 5/5

2.2.2 Partner Matching and Negotiation component

The PMN component is the one which has been fully integrated to the core platform, regarding both the data exchange and the user interface. PMN is crucial for almost every step of the product development process as it provides the opportunity to find potential partners at any stage of the development. This is why the integration of the component has been prioritised as shown in the Toylabs Platform integration plan (see previous section).

The following diagram represents the high-level architecture of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component. In the Presentation Layer the two main interfaces to the end users are being presented in the diagram, referring to Partner Searching and to establishing Business Agreements with selected partners.

Figure 9: high-level architecture of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component

The PMN component has the highest level of integration and for the end user could be considered as an actual part of the core platform. It allows the user to:

- Seek for collaborators based on specific criteria out from a pool of other users
- Get recommendations from the system regarding possible collaborators based on specific thresholds
- Send specific collaboration requests to other users identified through the search results
- Exchange contracts to seal an agreement for collaboration

Indicative screens of the component, as fully integrated in UI level, are presented next.

dsfsd
Search for Collaborators

Search by name...

ADVANCED SEARCH

I am looking for a: Toy Manufacturer FabLab Child Expert Safety Expert

That has any the following competencies:

<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Modelling	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning
<input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM and Structural Analysis Simulation	<input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling
<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing	<input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting
<input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting	<input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine
<input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming	<input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting

Scale of production needed: Prototyping Only Small Medium Large Extra Large

I will pay using: Bank Transfer Credit Card Paypal Check Bitcoin

Payment will be: On Delivery In 15 Days In 30 Days In 45 Days In 60 Days In 90 Days

Clear Search

Figure 10: Partner Matching Screenshot 1/3

Figure 11: Partner Matching Screenshot 2/3

Figure 12: Partner Matching Screenshot 1/3

2.2.3 Augmented Reality Feedback component

The Augment Reality Feedback component is - at the time the present deliverable is being compiled - under development. A prototype version of the component has been released but no integration in the Toylabs platform has taken place apart from an option to call the component from the platform as an external process.

As presented in the integration plan provided in the previous section, the first complete version of the ARF component will be ready for getting integrated in the 2nd release of the integrated platform on Month 15.

The following diagram represents the architecture of the component, showing in a clear way both the different screens as part of ARF user interface and the (to be built) connectors to the core platform at the application logic layer.

Figure 13: high-level architecture of the Augmented Reality Feedback Component

In principle, the ARF component shall be able to:

- Visualize existing Augmented Reality models and prepare them for public/private display to end users (manufacturers)
- Setup questionnaires linked to Augmented Reality models (manufacturers)
- Download Augmented Reality models and visualise them (end users)
- Provide comments and answer questionnaires linked to the downloaded Augmented Reality models (end users)

3 Components Integration Plan Update

3.1 Releases

According to the project schedule, at the time the present deliverable is being compiled, the 1st version of the Integrated platform has been released. In this version two out of the three main added value components have already been integrated (one fully and one partially) to the platform, while the third component is in development stage. As there are not significant deviations from the plan, the target of having at the next release a version of the integrated platform that all components will be fully integrated and working seamlessly is more than feasible as analysed next.

3.2 Integration Plan Update

Up to now, a gradual approach has been followed, having first the integration of the Partner Matching and Negotiation component successfully completed. The component is very close in terms of functions to the core platform operations and its integration is already at the highest level (UI) referring to the 1st release of the integrated platform.

The second component to be integrated is the Market & Trends Analysis. Although the component is more complicated than PMN regarding its operation and functions and is still under development, its integration at API level has been successfully completed. Before the second release of the platform in Month 15, the integration at user interface level is expected to be complete for this component as well.

Finally, the AR Feedback added-value component is to be integrated at the next release of the platform, at least at API level which is the most crucial part in terms of exchanging all required data. However, the complete UI integration of all the components is expected at the third (final) release of the platform.

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 At a glance

D4.2 accompanies the 1st release of the Toylabs Integrated Platform. It has provided an update of the architecture of the Platform itself as well as of the added value components and description of the integration progress of the components to the main platform.

4.2 Next Steps

The next steps include the completion of the integration of the Market Trends Analysis component in order to achieve UI integration level and a smooth integration of the Augmented Reality Feedback component which is still under development at the present time.

In general, the development process follows the plan and is partially ahead of schedule as far it concerns the Market Trends Analysis integration. Based on the feedback received and the progress on the development of the different components, minor amendments to the plan may be decided and – in such case – will be reported accordingly. However, it is expected that the Toylabs Collaboration Platform will be up and fully functional at its next release, in order to have enough time to get validated in action by the industrial users of the Toylabs consortium.